

Manifold Acceleration due to Bosonic Presence – 8 Theory

O Manor

June 23, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial equation of the coupling constants series, it is possible to reason for the reason to a unique, independent arrow of time that is one sided. The argument presented similar to intended base vectors from linear algebra.

Introduction

The first equation of the framework described by (1):

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.11)$$

The second equation of the framework, the coupling constants series, which proved bosons to be net curvature on the Lorentz manifold described by (1.12) – (1.16):

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.12)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.13)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.14)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.15)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.16)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.17)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g_i - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' \neq 0 \quad (1.18)$$

If we replace the usual construction, i.e. the fermions which vanish into matter, given by condition (1.11) to bosons which are net variations summing as positive given by (1.17) than the Lorentz manifold is no longer stationary, giving us equation (1.18). The physical meaning of such a construction than would be an acceleration of the metric, However if fermions accelerate toward each other due to their opposite signs, the bosons will not accelerate toward each other but rather toward a common spatial coordinate. Their behavior is effected by the first boson that arrives, as it creates net curvature and so increase the probability of arrival for other bosons. Since they all have the same sign as they are net curvature, i.e. they commute in physical theories. Such a description is in agreement with the nature of bosonic behavior and with the fact that bosonic particles can be concentrated or accelerated to a single point, behavior utilized by laser technology for example.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)